

Welcome to our joint newsletter #6! Get ready for the latest updates and insights from Climate Farm Demo and ClimateSmartAdvisors.

CLIMATE FARM DEMO MID-TERM ANNUAL MEETING

On June 4-5, 2024, the Climate Farm Demo (CFD) Mid-Term Annual Meeting took place online, attracting around 150 attendees. The agenda was packed with workshops designed for Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs), emphasizing their crucial role in the project. The interactive sessions highlighted the significance of such meetings for a project of this scope.

Christine Berger, the project coordinator, kick-started the event with an inspiring plenary session. She stressed punctuality and active engagement, detailing the CFD's goals to implement, demonstrate, and promote Climate Smart Farming across Europe. Christine also reported significant progress, including the successful recruitment and registration of all targeted farms, with most reporting completed on time.

A series of workshops followed, beginning with "Ways in which the CFA can support the PDF on their journey to climate smart farming." Facilitated by experts **Tom O'Dwyer**, **John Greaney**, and **Isidora Colic**, this workshop focused on strengthening the advisor-farmer relationships and sharing best practices and strategies for effective support.

Another key workshop provided practical insights on implementing mitigation and adaptation plans, highlighting the importance of structured audits and clear goal-setting processes. This session was facilitated by **Elena Bortolazzo**, **Lorena Giglio**, **Annika Harlo**, and **Henna Latvala**, who shared their field experiences and stressed the use of common templates for consistency across different levels.

RECAP OF DAY 2

The meeting on June 5th started with a dynamic session on "How to animate the national network of PDFs and CFAs?" facilitated by **András Vér**, **Krisztina Takács**, and **Laure Triste**. This workshop reviewed successful strategies and challenges within the national networks, fostering a proactive approach to knowledge exchange and network engagement.

The "Rewarding mechanisms and carbon farming – NC and CFA needs and questions" session at the CFD Midterm Annual Meeting, led by **Laurène Lebelt** from EIT Climate-KIC, centered on the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework (EU CRCF) and developing effective reward mechanisms.

The meeting concluded with a discussion on collaborative efforts led by **Luis Mira** and **Maria Mendonça** from CONSULAI. This session highlighted a case study from Climate Farmers, illustrating the impact of systemic thinking in expanding climate-smart farming, and showcased successful strategies that enrich CFD's work at EU and national levels.

This gathering not only reinforced the collaborative spirit vital for the success of the CFD project but also set a positive and determined tone for the continuation of impactful climate-smart farming initiatives. Thank you all for participating!

“
Congratulations to all our partners: Pilot DEMO Farmers, National Coordinators and Climate Farm Advisors first and foremost for having risen to the challenge of committing themselves fully to the project. We still have a few months to finalise the audits and the adaptation and mitigation plans and lay the foundations for our concrete Climate Smart Farming Practices. The first DEMO campaign has begun and we can all be very enthusiastic about what's to come!

Christine Berger
Climate Farm Demo Project Coordinator

LEARN MORE ABOUT THE
MEETING HERE

GENERAL ASSEMBLY RECAP

The ClimateSmartAdvisors General Assembly was hosted in **Jurmala, Latvia** from **April 23-25, 2024**. The event attracted **89 attendees** and featured a series of engaging workshops and sessions, focusing on the exchange of knowledge and strategies among climate smart advisors. The assembly spanned three days, providing a structured platform for collaboration and innovation.

[LEARN MORE](#)

“

After an intense first year of trying to set this large consortium in the correct position, the project is now ready to move into second gear, where various activities, such as the CoPs, the CoDIEs and the thematic knowledge exchange events, will now start feeding and animating the network.

Lies Debruyne
ClimateSmartAdvisors Project Coordinator

BELGIAN COP MEETING

Excited to announce the first Community of Practice meeting in Belgium, gathering five agricultural advisors from Flanders and Wallonia at the Boerenbond building in Leuven on May 14. Guided by their Climate Smart Coach, **Tom Schaecken**, the team includes experts from ELEVEO, ULIège and Boerenbond Projects, with experience in carbon footprinting and climate scans across various farming sectors. The initial session focused on enhancing the skills of climate-smart advisors through a practical approach, beginning with climate audits and culminating in actionable climate measures for farms. Motivated by their progress, the advisors have already planned a follow-up session and a site visit for June 28, embracing the motto "Union fait la force!" to strengthen their collaborative climate efforts in Belgium.

COP MEETING IN LUXEMBOURG

The first Community of Practice (CoP) meeting for CONVIS was held on May 14, 2024, in Ettelbruck, Luxembourg, focusing on the pressing issue of ammonia emissions in agriculture. Lasting 3.5 hours and attracting 15 participants from various CONVIS departments, the session included an overview of ammonia's role in the nitrogen cycle and its calculation methods. **Rocco Liroy**, national coordinator for the CSA project, facilitated the session, which concluded with plans for a follow-up meeting in July or August to further explore ammonia emission strategies, involving external experts and stakeholders.

CONNECTING WITH AKIS

Engaging with key stakeholders in the national Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) is essential for the success of climate smart advising and farming. This collaboration involves farmers, researchers, policymakers, and technology providers, enhancing the delivery of climate smart advice and expanding the project's reach. The Climate Smart AKIS (CS-AKIS) approach includes identifying key actors and obstacles in climate change mitigation and adaptation within agriculture. By prioritizing these stakeholders and updating the CS-AKIS Actors Communication and Engagement plan annually, we tailor engagement strategies to foster understanding, manage risks, and leverage opportunities effectively.

Special thanks to Marleen Gysen for this contribution.

Funded by
the European Union

These projects have received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreements No 101060212 and No 101084179

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright (C) 2024 Climate Farm Demo and ClimateSmartAdvisors. All rights reserved.

Want to change how you receive these emails?

You can [update your preferences](#) or [unsubscribe](#)

ClimateFarmDemo <climatefarmdemo@biosense.rs>
Reply-To: ClimateFarmDemo <climatefarmdemo@biosense.rs>
To: general.cfd@acta.asso.fr

Mon, Jun 17, 2024 at 10:34 AM

[Quoted text hidden]